

NATIONAL ARCHIVES OF AUSTRALIA MIGRATION OF BORN-DIGITAL RECORDS TO PRESERVICA

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Abstract - This paper examines the migration of born-digital records from the National Archives of Australia's original in-house developed digital preservation system to Preservica in 2022-23. In particular, the paper will discuss decisions made about data clean-up, what was to be migrated, the tools developed to facilitate the migration, issues that arose during the migration and how they were resolved. The paper also looks at the verification and audit process developed to ensure all objects and metadata were migrated and discuss lessons learned.

I. INTRODUCTION

The National Archives of Australia (NAA) is the official repository of the federal government. It is responsible for collecting, preserving and making publicly accessible government information appraised of having ongoing value regardless of format.

NAA has been accepting transfers of digital records since the early 1970s when they were typically transferred on media such as 9 track magnetic tape and stored in an off-line storage environment.[1] Since 2000 digital transfers have mainly consisted of digital files and metadata in a range of digital file formats exported from agency business systems or extracted from network shares.

This paper examines the planning and process for the migration of born-digital records from NAA's original digital preservation system developed in the 2000s. It does not discuss the migration of digitized content into Preservica or the migration of audiovisual files from the original system into NAA's audiovisual digital asset management system, Mediaflex.

To understand the decisions that needed to be made and the challenges encountered during the migration it is necessary to have a detailed look at NAA's original digital preservation system.

II. DIGITAL PRESERVATION AT THE NAA

The NAA was a relatively early starter in developing a digital preservation program. A project, called 'From Agency to Researcher' commenced in 2001 and aimed, amongst other things, to build a digital archive, that is the infrastructure for the long-term storage of digital records and a digital preservation software platform to undertake the preservation work and manage the workflows.

A. *The Green Paper: Concepts and Principles*

The conceptual basis of the project was detailed in a research paper, "An Approach to the Preservation of Digital Records," also known as the Green Paper.[2] The Green Paper was an important foundation document that formed the basis of subsequent software and infrastructure development. The document set out the basic conceptual approach to convert, or 'normalise', digital records into 'appropriate open (i.e. non-proprietary) and well-documented data formats, and to provide tools for viewing the preserved records. The approach was also to store Records and metadata together in an XML format (a markup language for storing structured data) files. To achieve this, records were converted to new formats and then encoded as 'text' and embedded into XML files along with technical and intellectual metadata.

The benefits of using XML were described as follows:

- XML is a widely used, fully documented standard for structuring digital documents;
- the XML specification is freely available and frees the organisation from dependence on particular IT vendors;
- XML can be used as a technology base indefinitely; and
- the creation of additional XML data formats to meet the preservation needs of many record types is not technically challenging.

The Green Paper articulated the concept of the performance model: 'In the case of digital records, archivists are not interested in the "original" records but in capturing and recreating the fleeting and temporary performance of that record as it was viewed.' A related concept discussed in the Green Paper is 'essence', that is, the characteristics of a record that must be preserved to maintain its meaning over time, a concept better known today as 'essential characteristics' or 'significant properties'.

The Green Paper also enunciated five fundamental principles that underpinned NAA's digital preservation program at that time:

The program:

1. must be able to preserve any digital record that is brought into National Archives' custody regardless of the application or system it is from or data format it is stored in;
2. must determine and preserve the essence of the digital records...and recreate their essential performance over time;
3. will be based on non-proprietary technologies;
4. will minimise the number of preservation treatments applied to each digital record;
5. will not limit the accessibility choices of the National Archives or of future researchers.

The Green Paper was well-received in the GLAM community and it set the digital preservation agenda at NAA for several years.

B. Digital Preservation Software Platform

The two main components of the digital preservation software suite were the Digital Preservation Recorder (DPR) and Xena (XML normalising of archives).

The Digital Preservation Recorder (DPR) was developed initially as a tool for recording an audit trail for digital preservation processing. The

application captured information (i.e. audit metadata) about each digital object as it passed through each step of the digital preservation process. However, once the prototype DPR was developed it became apparent immediately that the software should do more than record the actions of other software and that DPR should become a workflow management tool. DPR was then redeveloped to achieve that goal and provided the graphical user interface for each stage of the digital preservation process.

The process reflected reflects the physical infrastructure of the NAA digital repository:

1. Quarantine: in this phase, the data was checked against a manifest file (which included file-level information such as the checksum and file path) supplied by the agency and then scanned for viruses and malware using ClamAV, an open source anti-virus application.
2. Preservation: in this stage DPR used the Archives' digital preservation application, Xena (described below), to carry out the preservation treatment for each data object. Quality assurance of preserved digital records also took place to ensure that the 'essence' of the original record was maintained. As the process could not be automated, DPR generated a selection of normalised (i.e. migrated) records across record types (i.e. documents, spreadsheets, images, audio, etc.) and used the appropriate external applications to open both it and the original record so that the user could compare the two.
3. Digital Repository: the content of the carrying device was copied into the Digital Repository storage system.

Not only did DPR manage the workflow and capture audit metadata at every stage of the process (the data was stored in a postgresql database), it also managed the records in the repository, including reporting on digital records holdings and copying records out when they were requested.

Xena (XML electronic normalising of archives) was the software application that carried out preservation processing.

Preservation processing involved the creation of Xena files from each digital record. Each Xena file is an XML file that contained the content of the source

file as a base64 encoded bit stream and file-specific metadata (a process called binary normalisation). In addition, if a preservation file format had been determined by the NAA, Xena would convert a copy of the source file to that preservation file format and similarly embed it in a Xena file (a process called normalisation). Xena also extracted files from container formats such as ZIP, TAR, JAR and MAC Binary and normalized them into separate Xena files. The Xena files were what was stored and managed in the digital archive in a simple folder structure of year and transfer job number.

Although little used today in digital preservation approaches, Base64 encoding was a common method of storing file-specific XML metadata with the content of the digital record. At the time, the concept of a 'self-describing digital object' had a certain cachet - as all the content and metadata are stored in the same file, you do not need to maintain two separate files, and the link between them, over time. However, Base64 encoding did significantly inflate the size of files and the process was not necessarily reliable [3].

The file-specific XML metadata included file format information such as date last modified, date the Xena file was created, and the NAA unique identifier.

C. Digital Repository

Concurrent with the development of the digital preservation software platform, a digital repository was built based on the digital preservation principle of multiple independent storage (the original digital repository comprised two different flavours of RAID storage) and different software environments (Linux and Windows) though Linux was preferred.

A soft launch of NAA's digital archive occurred in 2007, however born-digital records were being ingested into the system prior to this as NAA had been accepting transfers of digital files since 2000 and there was a significant backlog of records stored on hard drives. By the time NAA acquired Preservica, following an approach to market for replacement digital systems, the digital repository held about ten million files consisting of six million binary normalised and four million normalised files. The format count amounted to over two hundred at that time.

D. Policy approach

Some of the policy and technical approaches that underpinned the original system are worth highlighting as they affected planning and decision-making for the migration to Preservica.

- Migration on ingest - channeling Jeff Rothenberg's influential dictum that 'digital objects last forever - or five years, whichever comes first,' NAA had early on adopted the view that preservation copies should be made as soon as possible.
- Open formats - NAA held the view that the only sustainable preservation formats were open, fully-specified formats. This meant that proprietary formats *per se* were regarded as at-risk, regardless of their ubiquity in the marketplace and completeness of published documentation.
- The focus on XML and base64 encoding was limiting, was not scalable in the long-term, and resulted in the creation of Xena files that required the Xena software to create and view them.

III. REPLACING THE DIGITAL PRESERVATION SOFTWARE PLATFORM

By 2017 the view at NAA was that the original digital preservation system was a 'burning platform' that needed to be replaced. There were a number of reasons for this:

- The digital preservation software platform had not been a focus of software improvement and ongoing iteration and as such was no longer regarded as a state-of-the-art digital preservation system.
- The system was completely decoupled from NAA's archival management system, RecordSearch. This significantly increased the risk of user error when accessioning and ingesting digital transfers.
- There were several widely used commercial and open source digital preservation systems available.
- Due to resource constraints and government policy settings, NAA had

moved away from open source development to commercial solutions.

- A policy decision that all digitization activity would result in a high resolution preservation master TIFF file that would be stored in the digital preservation system. Testing indicated that the existing digital preservation system was not scalable (the need to ingest millions of very large files).
- Digital preservation thinking had progressed in the years since the original system had been developed, and some of the concepts locked into the digital preservation system such as migration on ingest, the preference for open formats, and base64 encoding were no longer necessarily supported in the field.

IV. PRESERVICA

A tender process for replacement digital systems (following a period of requirements gathering) was undertaken in 2019 and resulted in Preservica being chosen to replace the digital preservation software platform.

Preservica is a long-term digital preservation system that is widely used by GLAM institutions, universities and organisations around the world. Preservica was originally developed as the “Safety Deposit Box” by Tessella Group in partnership with other organisations including the UK National Archives and became an independent company in 2015 when it split from Tessella.[4]

NAA acquired the Enterprise (on-premise) edition of Preservica and version 6.0 was deployed in 2019.

E. Integration of Preservica with the archival management system

Two software applications were developed using the .NET Framework as middleware integrating Preservica and the archival management system, RecordSearch.

Digital Archive Integration (DAI) facilitates the transfer process by creating transfer jobs (i.e. accessions) for digital transfers. DAI also allows users to query transfer jobs and digital objects for verification and reporting purposes. DAI also includes a background service to update or synchronize the archival information in Preservica when changes occur in RecordSearch archival data,

for example an item title or date a date field being updated or corrected.

Prepare Ingest Metadata (PIM) is the software application that carries out ingests into Preservica and prepares and loads technical metadata and archival metadata to Preservica and RecordSearch. The application consists of:

- a web user interface which is used to create, prepare, submit and monitor the progress of ingests
- a set of background services to prepare, backup, build and ingest Submission Information Packages (SIPs) into Preservica for loads.

PIM accesses SIPs that are located on a specified network drive. For born-digital transfers the SIP is a folder that contains digital objects (and retaining the original folder structure if that is provided by the transferring agency). SIPs for born-digital transfers are not tightly structured as transfers can originate from an large variety of different business systems, EDRMSs, share drives, email systems, websites, and enterprise systems like M365.

PIM generates a CSV file that contains system generated file-level metadata such as the checksum and file pathname, and placeholders for archival metadata such as item title, control symbol, disposal class and dates. The transferring agency provides the archival metadata as a mandatory part of the transfer process, and this is copied to the PIM CSV file. PIM normalizes metadata to the titles and format RecordSearch requires and uploads the metadata, creating new items in RecordSearch. This metadata is also written to Preservica. PIM also verifies the checksums provided by the agency. Finally, PIM validates the ingest against a number of file-level and item-level validations, for example errors are reported if an item identifier is not defined or not valid, checksums have not been computed for the file, the Transfer Job Number is not defined in RecordSearch, the file title is blank, the filename has invalid character, amongst other validations.

PIM also has other useful features, for example Thumbs.db files are ignored, the option to remove nested folders if they contain no files, and flagging low value files/objects such as 0 byte files, empty folders, and duplicate files in the same SIP.

These applications continue to be improved and developed in response to user needs and the evolving digital environment. The particular requirements and challenges of the migration prompted enhancements that have proved useful for subsequent transfers, as we will see below.

V. MIGRATION

In preparation for the migration a number of decisions needed to be made about what was to be exported from the digital preservation system for migration into Preservica. These included:

- Should both binary normalized and normalized files be migrated? After robust discussion there was agreement to migrate only the binary normalized files. There were a number of reasons for this decision: that we needed to revisit our migration policies, that we wanted to leverage Preservica's migration functionality, and that we weren't satisfied that migration had been successful in all cases.
- What metadata generated by DPR and Xena and stored in the Xena XML wrapper and the DPR database should be extracted and migrated Preservica? File-level metadata stored in DPR was quite minimalist and the fields that were identified for migration included file name, file path, item identifier, transfer job number, checksum and checksum algorithm. The audit metadata generated by DPR was not migrated, but a full backup copy of the DPR database was ingested into Preservica, so all data was preserved.
- Should the level of archival description be improved? Some groups of records had been described at a high level of aggregation. The decision was made that for certain groups of records we would take the opportunity to describe them at a more granular level (for example document or record level) to improve archival control and enhance accessibility.
- Transfer jobs containing wholly audiovisual records would be migrated to Mediaflex (some transfers containing a

mix of AV and non-AV would be migrated to Preservica to retain context).

- Under the NAA's own Records Authority, the key software applications Xena and DPR were appraised as being of ongoing archival value because of their significance.[5] It was agreed that final versions of software, including code and technical documentation would be formally transferred and ingested into Preservica.

In preparation for the migration we needed to reconcile archival metadata stored in RecordSearch and archival metadata stored in the DPR database, in particular item identifiers and transfer job numbers, as well as identify any missing records (i.e. digital records which had catalogue entries but which had not yet been ingested into DPR). A digital archive data quality report was generated by ICT and a process of error identification and data cleanup occurred. This reconciliation process was carried out over 2018-19 (at the time when we were developing requirements for the approach to market) and involved two staff members from ICT running data quality reports and correcting DPR database errors and two staff members from Collection Management Branch identifying the errors, correcting any RecordSearch errors, and ingesting missing records into the digital preservation system.

Extracting digital records from the digital preservation system required the development of an API Application (to run on the DPR server) and API client application to be run on the user desktop that reversed the base64 process for the binary normalized files and copied the resulting original files and XML metadata file for each agency transfer onto a designated network space retaining the DPR folder structure. The process was undertaken in March 2021 and the records extracted consisted of 6,251,099 files comprising 385 transfer jobs and 2,644,229 archival items. Total size was 3.5TB.

These transfer jobs were ingested into Preservica between in the 12 months between June 2021 and June 2022. The length of time taken is partly explained by competing priorities as ingest activity was happening alongside business-as-usual work. The ingest process highlighted several issues that required troubleshooting and enhancements to the PIM tool:

- Ingest errors occurred for files with file names that exceeded the Windows file path limit of 260 characters, contained Windows invalid file name characters and included consecutive spaces (Preservica issue). These typically resulted from files created in Apple or Linux environments. A two-pronged approach was adopted to deal with this issue. Firstly, in some instances file names were manually changed to remove invalid characters. Changes were made to PIM to avoid the (Windows) file path limit. Secondly, for problem files belonging to complex, software dependent items, where changing the file name might affect performance or rendering, the entire item was zipped and then ingested alongside the unzipped copy, which allowed the problem file(s) to be ingested without alteration.
 - 288 Thumbs.db files were found to have been ingested into the original digital preservation system. These were deleted and PIM revised to ignore these files if they are present in SIPs.
 - Similarly, 101 0 byte files were deleted, while four others were zipped and ingested because they were thought to support item functionality. Again, PIM was revised to flag SIPs containing 0 byte files.
 - Several thousand TIFF and PDF files had JHOVE errors. In the majority of instances, the files could be accessed and rendered in Preservica and in the desktop environment, and nothing more was done to investigate and remediate the failures. A small subset of files attracted JHOVE errors that indicated the files were corrupted and could not be accessed or rendered. In these cases it was evident the files had been transferred from the agency to us in that form.
 - A small number of files failed the checksum validation. Investigation found that the checksum of some MS Office formats changed when staff had opened files to check the contents using editing software rather than viewers.
 - One PST file was flagged by ClamAV (anti-virus app) as infected with a virus. Testing in a stand-alone network confirmed this was not the case and the file was zipped and ingested.
- Following completion of the migration a process of validation and verification was undertaken by Collection Management and ICT staff in a series of spreadsheets, which included spreadsheets for corrupt files, fixity check reviews, file name changes, files zipped prior to ingest, item identifier changes, thumbs.db audit and repository cross check/reconciliation. A master spreadsheet confirmed all quality assurance checks and a formal minute confirming completion was signed off at executive level.

VI. CONCLUSION

The migration resulted in numerous lessons learned ranging from the high level to lessons specific to particular archival activities, including:

- The deficiencies of key business systems that are not integrated (in this case the digital preservation software platform was completely decoupled from the archival management system, which led to numerous instances of user error).
- The importance of cross-Branch engagement and detailed planning to ensure appropriate and appropriately skilled resources are committed to the work.
- The need to appraise, validate and verify born-digital transfers at the pre-ingest stage.
- A one-size-fits-all approach to digital transfers is not feasible or appropriate. Each digital transfer has unique features and requirements that necessitate an individual response.
- The importance of data quality control and robust quality assurance processes, including final audit and sign-off.
- Ongoing enhancement and improvement of software tools and infrastructure in response to user needs and the evolving digital environment.

The migration of the born-digital component was just one part of a long and complex migration of digital files into Preservica. Tens of millions of

preservation TIFF files, the product of digitization work, were also migrated from network shares and hard drives. As of September 2025, ongoing business as usual digital transfers and digitization work has resulted in Preservica managing 60 million files, over 300 formats, and ingest rates as much as 4tb per day.

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AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

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